

Figure 1. The ammonia decomposition reaction on Cu-Fe and Cu-Ru AR photocatalysts. (A) Comparison of photocatalysis and thermocatalysis for both ARs. Reactions were performed under differential reactor conditions ($< 2\%$ reactant conversion), to avoid mass transfer limitations. Error bars represent standard deviations among three independent measurements. (B) Macroscopic kinetics studies: (top) the reaction orders of reactant, (bottom) the apparent activation barriers E_a . A power of 0 mW refers to thermocatalysis. (C) Wavelength-dependent reaction rates. (Inset) Optical absorption spectra. (D) Calculated wavelength-dependent hot-carrier injection rate with the anti-bonding orbital (ϵ_0) positioned at 0.2, 0.5, and 0.8 eV above Fermi level E_F . (Inset) Schematic of the HC injection model.

Figure 2. First-principles quantum mechanical studies of photocatalytic ammonia decomposition. (A) Plane-wave density-functional theory with the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof exchange-correlation functional and D3 Becke-Johnson damping corrections (DFT-PBE-D3BJ) optimized structures along the MEP for NH_3 dissociative adsorption on a Cu-Fe alloy surface. (B) Ground and excited-state emb-CASPT2 PESs along the MEP in (A) for the spin eigenstates: singlet (green), triplet (red), quintuplet (blue). Solid, straight, orange arrows represent vertical excitation and de-excitation, and dashed, curly, orange arrows represent productive (thermal) pathways. (C) The DFT-PBE-D3BJ optimized structures along the MEP for associative desorption of N_2 . (D) Ground and excited-state emb-CASPT2 PESs along the MEP in (C) for the spin eigenstates, (inset) enlarged PESs at 0 to 4 Å. (E) Schematic comparison of the energy landscape for photocatalysis (excited states) and thermocatalysis (ground state) on Cu-Fe and Cu-Ru. Red arrows refer to electronic excitation on Fe-N, and blue to Ru-N. Only the two possible RDSs are included for simplicity; migrations of nitrogen species are not considered for the same reason.

Figure 3. Electrified photocatalysis of ammonia decomposition for gram-scale H₂ production. (A) Photograph of the reaction cell (left) and the photocatalytic platform (right) using LEDs at 470 nm for ammonia decomposition. The reaction cell consisted of two concentric tubes of different diameters, with the catalyst (~0.5 cm bed thickness) filled in between them. (B) Ammonia conversion and corresponding H₂ production rates on the Cu-Fe and Cu-Ru catalysts as a function of delivered LED power at ammonia space velocity 487 hr⁻¹, which is defined as the volumetric flow rate of ammonia divided by the volume of the catalyst (11 cm³). (C) Ammonia conversion, H₂ production, and energy efficiency as a function of the feed space velocity during ammonia decomposition on the Cu-Fe catalyst under illumination power of 140 W. (D) Long-term photocatalytic ammonia decomposition on the Cu-Fe catalyst under an illumination power of 137 W (light on at time = 0). In each case, measurements were performed using ~3.7 g catalyst (60-120 mesh size that is the catalyst powder size of 250-125 μm) and without supplying external heating.